

PROMOTING CHILD-FRIENDLY SCHOOL PRACTICES IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL FOR AN IMPROVED LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

Educators must foster child-centeredness and a school environment where all learners are cared, accepted and respected as human beings. In line to this, Department of Education adapted the Child-Friendly School System (CFSS) initiative: One, in which it recognizes and respects children's rights and responsibilities; provides the enabling environment to realize children's right in school; and helps ensure such an environment in the community and household are child-friendly. This study was an attempt to identify the relationship of child-friendly school practices and its learning environment in public elementary school in Tiaong II District, Division of Quezon. This study is a descriptive -correlational kind of research which uses a survey questionnaire. There were 120 teacher-respondents coming from thirteen schools in Tiaong II District, Division of Quezon, conducted last March 2021. Results showed that out of 120 respondents majority were above 35 years old and females. Most of them were married, having bachelor's degree with MA units and rendered 5-10 years in teaching. Respondents from Tiaong II District, Division of Quezon believed that the level of implementation of child-friendly school practices in their school in terms of inclusiveness, gender-sensitive, effectiveness, healthy, caring and protective and involves children's families and community were "very much practiced". Respondents also revealed that their school level of implementation in terms of school learning environment such as school physical facilities, adequacy of learning materials, school programs and activities, school services, bullying and accident cases and human resources were "very highly evident". Overall results on the perception of the respondents on the relationship of child-friendly school practices and its learning environment is very significant. Thus respondents believed that child-friendly school practices have greater impact on its learning environment. This study hopefully contributes to all public elementary schools - administrators and teachers - the relevance of providing child-friendly school environment for all children. They may update their knowledge and skills in the implementation of the CFSS by monitoring additions or changes in its principles.

Keywords: child-friendly school, learning environment, children's rights, descriptive -correlational